

Emotional Intelligence and Aggression among Adolescent Students in High Schools

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Abstract: The study aimed to determine the assess role of Emotional Intelligence on Aggression among adolescent high school students. Emotional intelligence is based on the concept of understanding one's own emotions and that of others. Aggression is categorized by hurtful and destructive behaviour towards others; it seems to oppose the empathetic nature of Emotional Intelligence. This ex-post facto research study involved 38 boys and 38 girls between age group 14 yrs. and 18 yrs. - who got selected through convenient sampling technique. The scales Aggression by Buss & Perry (1992) and Emotional Intelligence by Dr. AK Singh and Dr. Shruti Narayan (2014) have been used to measure the Emotional Intelligence. Pearson's Correlations, Regression, Two-Way factorial Anova and t tests were used to establish test results. Analysis indicated significant negative relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Hostility ($r=-0.328$, $p<.01$). Hostility showed a negative correlation with Empathy and Handling Relations respectively ($r= -0.276$, $p <.01$) and ($r= -0.318$, $p<.01$). This clearly indicated that Emotional Intelligence or its dimensions increased, the Hostility among students decreased. Empathy and Aggression showed a significant negative relationship ($r=-0.231$, $p <.05$) indicating if Empathy among students is more, their Aggression level is controlled. Anger portrayed a negative correlation with Understanding Emotions ($r= -0.261$, $p <.05$).

Tukey simultaneous confidence intervals showed significant difference in the confidence interval for the difference between the mean range of LEI and HEI as 5.192 to 12.072. There exists a significant difference in-between group levels of emotional intelligence (HEI, MEI & LEI) on aggression of adolescent male students but not female students. Tukey simultaneous difference between the group on aggression across the various Emotional levels of the male and female students indicated significant difference in LEI and HEI at .05 level.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence, Adolescence, Aggression.

Introduction

Adolescence typically describes the years between ages 13 and 19 and can be considered the transitional stage from childhood to adulthood. However, the physical and psychological changes that occur in *adolescence* can start earlier, during the preteen or "teen" years (ages 9 through 12).

Recognizing adolescence

Adolescence is a period of life with specific health and developmental needs and rights. It is also a time to develop knowledge and skills, learn to manage emotions and relationships, and acquire attributes and abilities that will be important for enjoying the adolescent years and assuming adult roles. All societies recognize that there is a difference between being a child and becoming an adult. How this transition from childhood to adulthood is defined and recognized differs between cultures and over time. In the past it has often been relatively rapid, and in some societies it still is. In many countries, however, this is changing.

Adolescent Thought Structure

Cognitive schemas and aggressive behaviour in adolescents: the mediating role of social information processing -Crucial Needs for an Adolescent due to their individuality

The changes that take place during adolescence suggest nine observations with implications for health policies and programmes:

- Adolescents need parents to be unequivocal and sensitive towards their needs.
- All Adolescents are not the same hence comparison and demining them may lead to unfavorable consequences.
- Some adolescents are particularly vulnerable and highly sensitive to situations.
- Adolescent development has repercussions on adolescent health.
- Adolescent development has health implications throughout life.
- Unforeseen / unexpected changes during adolescence distress how adolescents think and act.
- Adolescents need to understand the processes taking place in their system during this phase and be comfortable with their organic body cathexis.
- To contribute positively, adults need to accept and support the processes taking place during adolescence development.

Adolescence and Parent-Child Relationship – Inception of Aggression

Adolescence is a transitional stage of physical and mental human development generally occurring between puberty and legal adulthood, which marks an important turning point in the parent child relationship. As the child enters adolescence, the biological, cognitive, and emotional changes of the period spark transformations in the parent-child relationship. In many homes, the transition into adolescence coincides with the parent's transition into midlife, and this, too, may introduce additional challenges into the family system that spill over into the parent-child relationship.

Adolescence is a time during which the child urges for independence may challenge parent's authority, as the young adolescent strives to establish a sense of emotional autonomy or individuation. Adolescents fare best and their parents are happiest when parents can be both encouraging and accepting of the child's needs for more psychological independence.

Emotional Intelligence

In these two concepts of the Mayor and Salovey - tried to explore much out of it but the real concept get popularized in the mainstream of society by the person known as Daniel Goleman. There are two concepts emerging out of the topic Emotional Intelligence – one is Emotion and the other is Intelligence. Important questions are -Does emotional intelligence consist of emotion or intelligence? If yes, what is the interrelationship between these two concepts? Looking into the origin of emotional intelligence we often talk about two is it intelligence that is derived from out of emotions or emotions has given birth the concept of intelligence. There are lots of reasons because emotion is the root cause of human survival.

- What is an emotion?
- What is the different nature and functions of emotions and what are the different applications of emotions?
- What is the essence of bringing intelligence into the domain of emotions then probably conclude about the emergence of the concept emotional intelligence?

Examining the concept of Emotions – certain concepts directly relate to emotional intelligence. One is called emotion intelligence creativity and wisdom. Basically emotion has been defined as “*the inner conscious state that we infer ourselves and others. Emotions sometimes are called the private experiences.*”

Emotional Intelligence --- According to Daniel Goleman, “emotional intelligence is a master aptitude, a capacity that profoundly affects all other abilities, either facilitating or interfering with them”. The term emotional intelligence encompasses the following five characteristics and abilities: 1. Self-awareness 2. Self-management 3. Self-Motivation 4. Empathy 5. Social skills

Emotional Intelligence involves Self-Control, Zeal and Persistence. Emotional Intelligence helps us develop stable and trusting relationships and they by interpret the actions of others. Emotional Quotient can be learned and unlearned.

According to Lisa, J.M (2004), "Emotional maturity brings with it a capacity for independence, the willingness to take action as for agent along with the capacity affiliate; it's freely initiate and sustains loving relationships."

Implications of Emotional Literacy

- Competencies → Promote Creativity, resilience and connection
- Values → Develop bigger outlook and integrated self
- Outcomes → Like quality of Life, relations and performance

Psychologists describe emotional intelligence or Emotional Quotient (EQ) as consisting of the following:

- The ability to face challenges by being aware of one's own self;
- Ability to find positive ways of dealing with stressful situations;
- Communicating effectively and politely with others;
- Empathizing with people;
- Willingness to form healthier relationships by working closely with people;
- Ability to use all these qualities to achieve success at work and in life.

Why adolescents need high emotional intelligence?

Adolescents who are academically sharp may sometimes be socially and interpersonally incompetent. Despite possessing a high IQ, success may not automatically follow. But by increasing the emotional quotients, the adolescents can become more productive and successful at what they do. High emotional intelligence will definitely help an adolescent to reduce stress by decreasing conflict, improving relationships and better understanding.

Emotional Intelligence has become increasingly popular as a measure for identifying potentially effective leader and it may use as a tool in developing effective leadership skills. (George,2000; Jooste, 2004).

5 Key components of Emotional Intelligence

1. Self - Awareness: Having a deep understanding of the SWOT i.e. Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats, Needs and Drives:-

- Emotional Awareness relates to – Ability to recognize one’s own Emotions and their effects
- Self Confidence: self-worth and capabilities

2. Self – Regulation: Ongoing conversation people have with themselves, which frees them from the being of a prisoner of their feelings. It involves:-

- Self- Control : Manage disruptive impulses
- Trustworthiness: Maintain honesty and integrity
- Conscientiousness : Take responsibility for own performance
- Adaptability: Handle changes with flexibility
- Innovation: be Open to new ideas

3. Motivation: it requires clear goals and positive attitudes. It is made up of →

- Achievement drive or strive to improvement
- Commitment to aligning with the goals
- Initiative & Optimism

4. Empathy: Ability to sense what others are feeling? An empathetic person excels at:-

- Service Orientation
- Developing others
- Leveraging diversity Understanding Others
- Political Awareness

5. Social Skills: Development of good interpersonal skills is tantamount to success in life and career. Social skills include:-

- Influence
- Communication
- Leadership
- Change Catalyst
- Conflict Management
- Building Bonds
- Collaboration and cooperation
- Team Capabilities

Aggressive behaviour in adolescents

Aggression may be defined as harmful behaviour which violates social conventions and which may include deliberate intent to harm or injure another person or object (Bandura, 1973; Berkowitz, 1993). Important distinctions among aggressive subtypes include: level of planning, appreciation for consequences, and affective intensity associated with the aggressive acts.

Based on these distinctions, researchers investigating aggressive subtypes in human adults and young children have commonly concluded that there is a dichotomy of aggressive subtypes that have variously been described as: [a] impulsive, reactive, affective, or non-planned; and [b] premeditated, proactive, instrumental, predatory, or controlled (e.g., Heilbrun et al., 1978; Coccaro, 1989; Atkins et al., 1993; Barratt et al., 1997a; Vitaro et al., 2002; McEllistrem, 2004). For the purpose of this investigation, the terms impulsive aggression and premeditated Anderson & Huesmann, (2003) defined aggression as a behaviour directed towards another individual carried out with the proximate (immediate) intent to cause harm”. Aggression is a complex behaviour that has been studied from a wide array of theoretical perspectives including the psychoanalytical theory of Freud (Gross, 1992), the ethological theory of Lorenz (1966), and the social learning theory of Bandura (1963). Additionally, theorists have proposed that aggression exists in many different forms (Berkowitz & Donnerstein, 1982; Buss, 1961; Dodge & Coie, 1987; Moyer, 1976). Consequently, there is disagreement about the most suitable way to define and measure the construct of aggression.

The following definition offered by Baron and Richardson (1994) as being representative of the construct: “Aggression is any form of behaviour directed toward the goal of harming or injuring another living being who is motivated to avoid such treatment.”

Statement of the problem

The purpose of the study is to investigate the possible correlations between Emotional Intelligence and Aggression in male and female adolescent students in high schools. The following questions were specifically asked:

1. Is Emotional Intelligence significantly correlated with aggression?
2. Are there aspects or variables of the Emotional Intelligence that significantly correlate with aggression?
3. Are there aspects or variables of Aggression that significantly correlate with Emotional Intelligence?
4. Are there significant differences in gender with respect to aggression and Emotional Intelligence?

Significance of the Study

The high school years of children are co-terminus with their early adolescence and post puberty years. Exposure to Media, occupations hazards of parents and crowding have caused a significant impact in shaping the children. The need for helping young boys and girls deal with problems of growing up is great. They tend to become emotionally highly stung, develop fads and fetishes, and if not suitably helped to outlive them, they may become emotionally crippled. Research show that IQ accounts for only about 20 percent of a person success in Life. The balance can be attributed to EQ. IQ is a measure of intelligence quotient whereas EQ is a measure of Emotional quotient.

The adolescents have individualistic ideas, interests and emotions and are keen to express them, looking forward to proper recognition and encouragement. Close bonding and entrusted relationship like family and friends, inculcate these desirable attitudes, interests and goals to flourish and take shape. If problems continue to be neglected or unresolved, with no valid insight, it could assume tremendous proportions.

This study will help in creating awareness and educate the young minds, teachers and parents. The most essential factors of understanding Emotional Intelligence during developing years will help in controlling Juvenile Delinquency and empower adolescents to channelize their emotional impulsiveness assertively. Developing and Balancing EGO is the most crucial and challenging job of the environment the individual gets nurtured in the developing days of his or her life.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The concept of emotional intelligence proposes that intelligence may understand emotion, and that emotion may facilitate intelligence (Mayer & Ciarrochi, 2006). According to Akinboye (2002) “no human action, whether good or bad, is emotion free”. Emotional intelligence is one of the important variables and has greater influence on human character. It has a pivotal role in the success of various domain of life. The basic emotions are happiness, interest, surprise, fear, anger, sorrow and disgust. According to Leventhal (1982) each of these emotions are operating through a control mechanism which serve as a monitor for one of the main aspects of human life. Controlling one’s emotions does not happen automatically. This can be done when someone is in touch with his inner as well as outer world. Each individual expresses emotion differently and ineffective expression of emotion creates abnormality within the person. Mental health is related with adequate expression of emotion.

In a study on effects of an emotional intelligence intervention on aggression and empathy among adolescents – it was aimed at exploring the effects of a two-year intervention grounded in the ability model of emotional intelligence (EI) on aggression and empathy among adolescents. Eight Spanish public schools volunteered

to participate in the research. A total of 590 adolescents (46% boys) were randomly assigned to either the EI training group or control group conditions. Students in the EI training group reported lower levels of physical/verbal aggression, anger, hostility, personal distress and fantasy compared to students in the control group. Additionally, the EI program was particularly effective for males' empathic abilities. These findings confirm the effectiveness of social and emotional learning interventions in Spanish academic contexts and extend the literature of gender-related differences during adolescence. Study limitations and future research directions are also considered.

Emotional Intelligence is a relatively new construct, but its roots can be seen as early as the 1920s in E.L. Thorndike's concept of social intelligence, "the ability to perceive one's own and others' internal states" (Mayer & Salovey, 1993, p.435). Social intelligence, however, focused too closely on the manipulation of inner states, so Salovey and Mayer came up with a more developed concept called emotional intelligence in the 1980s (Grewal & Salovey, 2006). Their EI concept pertains more to understanding emotions and is defined as "the ability to monitor one's own and other's feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them and to use this information to guide one's thinking and actions" (Salovey & Mayer, 1990, p.189). Since the 1980s, however, it has been defined and redefined so many times it is impossible to limit the definition of emotional intelligence to one specific phrase.

Essentially, it is a concept based on understanding emotions as critical. Emotional intelligence acts as a more pervasive and accurate predictor of success in life than traditional intelligence constructs (Qualter *et al.*, 2007). In fact, 80% of life successes can be attributed to emotional intelligence (Goleman, 1995). High emotional intelligence levels have been correlated with a myriad of benefits and positive life outcomes. Advantages include high levels of happiness, health, well-being, better academic performance and an increased ability to cope with change (Qualter *et al.*, 2007; Salami, 2011). The capacity to understand and decipher emotions is correlated with choosing and succeeding in a meaningful line of work, as well as with success in building lasting and significant relationships (Grewal & Salovey, 2006). This is not just true of adults; adolescents who have more advanced emotional abilities show lower stress levels, fewer signs of aggression, and demonstrate a smaller likelihood of involvement with drugs and alcohol (Qualter *et al.*, 2007). Abraham (1999) contended that those individuals who have higher levels of emotional intelligence have stronger ability to empathize, generally leading to their ability to conform better to organizational requirements.

Just as high levels of emotional intelligence are beneficial, low levels create recognizable deficits. Importantly, however, the problems caused by low levels of EI are not just the absence of those beneficial traits exemplified by those with high EI. Low levels of EI have been correlated with some forms of mental illness, including depression, borderline personality disorder and most notably Alexithymia (a difficulty processing emotional information; Grewal & Salovey, 2006). Those with low EI levels also tend to have a hard time understanding situations from the perspective of others and therefore tend to be less empathetic (Henley & Long, 1999). Emotional intelligence, then, seems deeply related to aggression and offending, however, this relationship has not been tested in depth.

The primary purpose of this project was to test this relationship. We predicted that emotional intelligence would relate to offending because individuals who have a higher emotional intelligence should be more able to follow the rules set by society, therefore being less likely to commit crimes. Those with high levels also tend to be more able to moderate their emotions and respond less easily to impulse. On the other hand, low levels should cause individuals to be more prone to risky behaviour. They also may be less able to recognize that their behaviour is risky, or that it has implications for others. We focused on whether this divorce from the reality of emotion leads individuals with low EI levels to have higher levels of aggression.

Aggression is primarily a learned behaviour and it can be learned from a variety of different sources and in different ways. There are four dimensions to the learning environment of a child: instigation, reinforcement, identification and sociocultural norms. Each of these dimensions plays a specific role in how a child learns to express aggression. The first, instigation, is when a child is in frustrating condition such as being rejected by their parents, and their drive increases along with their aggression. Reinforcement describes the nature of the parental response to a child acting aggressively; primarily, when a child is rewarded for aggressive behaviours, they will likely act that way again. Identification is both the adolescents internalizing the standards of their parents and also how they act out the behaviour they see from their parents and other adults.

This can be especially detrimental when those parents or adults act aggressively. Lastly, the norms of a youth's society and culture maybe more or less accepting of aggressive attitudes, causing certain actions to be seen ashore acceptable (Eron, 1987).

Aggression is directly linked with emotion and it determines one's behaviour, personality and integrity. It determines the nature of an individual. Emotional the person. Mental health is related with adequate expression of emotion. Adequate expression of emotion is related with the ability to understand, perceive and control one's and other's emotion. Aggression is directly linked with emotion and it determines one's behaviour, personality and integrity. It determines the nature of an individual. Emotional intelligence is related with empathy (Ciarrochi, Chan, and Caputi, 2000). Research evidence shows that there exist a significant negative correlation between emotional intelligence and aggression.

There are two overarching forms of aggression: indirect and direct (Card *et al.*, 2008). Though their definitions do overlap, indirect aggression includes behaviours such as gossiping and exclusion without direct confrontation; behaviours that harm through rejection. Two types of indirect aggression are social and relational aggression. Social aggression comes from a child's desire to be accepted in a group, but accomplishing this in a way that attacks or rejects others, perhaps by spreading a rumor about them. Relational aggression is when a child harms others by manipulating their peers through exclusion from the group and other means. Direct aggression includes both physical and verbal aggression, particularly direct attacks on personal well-being. Both direct and indirect aggression are inter correlated and associated with various factors of youth maladjustment (Card *et al.*, 2008). Physical aggression, a type of direct aggression, has been shown to perpetuate itself, particularly when it starts during the elementary school years (Broidy *et al.*, 2003). Physical aggression during this time increases the risk that this physical violence, in addition to other nonviolent delinquency, will continue into the adolescent years. In this particular case the results were specific to males, though boys and girls experience similar development of physical aggression (Broidy *et al.*, 2003).

Gender differences in aggression are also frequently noted in psychological literature. A meta-analytical study of 63 studies examining gender differences in adult aggression confirmed these findings although the overall difference between males and females was small (Eagley & Steffen, 1986). According to Connor (2004), males have been found to be more aggressive than females across various types of cultures, scientific studies, and categories of aggression. Buss (2005) has reported that males are believed to be more physically aggressive than females from an early age and commit the vast majority of murders. Thus gender plays an important role in human aggression. However, some empirical studies have found the discrepancy in male and female aggression to be more pronounced in childhood and the gender difference in adults to be modest. Still, there is evidence that males are quicker to aggression (Frey *et al.* 2009) and more likely than females to express their aggression physically. On the basis of a meta-analytical review of 148 studies on gender differences in overt and relational aggression, Card and associates (2008) have revealed that males are more overtly aggressive than females but when relational aggression was taken into consideration, females were often found to be just as aggressive as males.

Studies show that females in general have better control over their emotions in comparison to males. Also, males are more likely to retaliate when provoked to gain recognition; females are less likely to retaliate in a violent way because they are shielded by moral sense. Earlier researchers have demonstrated that both genetic and environmental factors play a role in a variety of behaviours in humans and animals (e.g. Grigorenko & Sternberg, 2003, but the genetic or biological basis of aggression, however, remains poorly understood).

Emotional intelligence (EI) is a concept based on understanding one's own emotions and the emotions of others. Because aggression is often categorized by hurtful and destructive behaviour towards others, it seems to oppose the empathetic nature of EI. In this study, we sought to test this relationship directly in the context of juvenile delinquency. We predicted that EI would be negatively correlated with aggression, and also relate to sex and offense type. Participants were ten detained youth at the Walla.

Walla Juvenile Justice Center and were tested using the Bar-On EQI: YV (S) and the Aggression Questionnaire to measure their emotional intelligence and aggression levels. We found that lower emotional intelligence levels were correlated with higher aggression scores, and that participants scored

the highest in physical aggression. Findings are discussed in terms of teaching EI in rehabilitation programs for youth offenders.

Research Question

The basic research question addresses the relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Aggression. The research literature reviewed leads to the predictions that Emotional Intelligence will correlate negatively with Aggression and therefore predict aggression.

- 1) Whether Emotional Intelligence is a contributor to Aggression?
- 2) Whether any of the dimensions of Emotional Intelligence predict Aggression?
- 3) Whether male and female students differ on the variables of Emotional Intelligence and Aggression and its dimensions?

To address these questions statistical techniques of Product moment Correlation, t-test and Multiple Regression will be used to examine Emotional Intelligence predictors in comparison with the four component sub traits (Anger, Hostility, Verbal or Physical Aggression) as defined in Aggression Questionnaire by Buss and Perry (1992).

Flow of Concept – Emotional Intelligence Vs Aggression

Objective

The study intends to find out the relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Aggression level of the high school students. In the light of above mentioned statement of the problem, following objectives of the study have been made:

- To assess Emotional Intelligence among high school students.
- To assess Aggression among the High School students.
- To assess the relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Aggression as well as the dimensions of Emotional Intelligence –Understanding Emotions Understanding Motivation Empathy Handling Relations and the dimensions of Aggression– Physical Aggression, Verbal Aggression, Anger and Hostility among the high school students.
- To study the influence of gender in Emotional Intelligence and Aggression variables among the students.
- To study the influence of High, Medium and Low Emotional Intelligence on Aggression in high school students.

Conceptual Model

Methodology

The aim of this study on Emotional Intelligence and Aggression of the adolescent high schools students is to assess the relationship of the various levels of the Emotional Intelligence and how it may correlate with their Aggression levels.

Data Source

Primary Sources of data are utilized by which data collected directly from the selected sample to this study. No Secondary sources of data were available for this study. Questionnaire method of data collection is utilized for this investigation of the study. In these Questionnaires, the questions are to be printed in such a way that there is facility for the respondents to reply them without much difficulty, along with that there was instructions provided verbally to improve a common base of understanding amongst the group of students. These Questionnaires elicits detailed quantitative and qualitative information's from the respondents.

The Emotional Intelligence scores are Dichotomous Scale (Turned into scores from Responses Yes or No), Aggression Scores item responses were Ordinal Data (Ranked in the correct order) but sum of the individual data is Nominal Scale for Statistical calculation.

Sampling Plan

For this ex-post facto research design - a non-probability sampling technique 'Convenient Sampling Method' was adopted for the data collection.

Universe of study: Various schools with classes IX to XII with students between age group 14 to 18 years. This facilitates comparison between the students of various departments with consideration of Gender and Family Background.

Sample of study: Selected adolescent high school students from various matriculation and higher secondary schools with equal number of boys and girls.

Sampling Size: 76

Tools

1. Emotional Intelligence

Emotional Intelligence scale was used for data collection. Emotional Intelligence scale is developed by Dr. Arun Kumar Singh and Dr. Shruti Narain in 2014. The present scale can be used to measure the Emotional Intelligence has 31 Items and four dimensions, i.e. understanding emotions, understanding motivation, Empathy and Handling Relations in a person's daily life. It was found to be 0.86 reliability and validity is 0.86.

2. Aggression

The Buss-Perry Aggression Questionnaire by Buss, A.H. & Perry, M. (1992). The aggression questionnaire. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 63(3), 452-459.

This 29-item questionnaire contains brief statements (e.g., Once in a while I can't control my urge to strike another person.) to which a rater assigns a number ranging from 1 to 5, where 1 = Not like me at all, and 5 =

A lot like me. This questionnaire yields a Total score and four subscale scores: RELIABILITY MEASURED BY CRONBACH'S A

- Full Scale .93
- Physical Aggression .82
- Verbal Aggression.73
- Anger .79
- Hostility .85

Data Analysis

The present study followed a 2X2 Factorial Design of Research. Anova, Regression Analysis, Correlation, Mean, Standard Deviation, t-test etc. were computed to analyse the data. Two- Way Analysis of variance were conducted to show the within group and between group differences along with the interaction effects for both the independent variables.

Operational Definition

- EI - Emotional Intelligence: Emotional Intelligence is a set of factors which involve awareness of self and managing emotions, developing oneself through the power of empathy and motivation and building strong relation with people (Samira Malekar 2005).
- Understanding Emotions: An individual's capacity to identify emotions in one's and others physical states, feelings and thoughts.
- Understanding Motivation: A high achievement drive together with the tendency to be optimistic and take initiative.
- Empathy: Ability to identify oneself mentally with others and to understand a person or thing accurately and read how other people feel, understand their perspectives, develop others, diverge diversity, read the mood of a group discern political realities and a tendency to take an interest in the lives of others.
- Handling Relations: To be able to manage and handle relation with others in a better way.
- Aggression: Feelings of anger or antipathy resulting in hostile or violent behaviour; readiness to attack or confront.
- Physical aggression: Behaviour causing or threatening physical harm towards others. It includes hitting, kicking, biting, using weapons, and breaking toys or other possessions.
- Verbal aggression: An assault on another's self-concept, rather than his/her position. Individuals who rely on verbal aggressiveness are viewed as less credible, have less satisfying relationships.
- Anger: A strong feeling of annoyance, displeasure. Psychological arousal and preparation for aggression (Buss & Perry, 1992).
- Hostility: Behaviour portraying unfriendliness or opposition. A feeling of ill will and injustice. (Buss & Perry, 1992)

Scoring for the EI scale

The answers of those items which tallied with answers given in the scoring key were given a score of +1. If they didn't tally, a score of zero was given. The scoring key is provided in Table below:-

Sr. No.	Dimensions	Items	Serial wise Items No.	Count	Total
I.	Understanding Emotions	Positive	5,15,18,28	4	4
		Negative	-	-	
II.	Understanding Motivation	Positive	3,7,9,12,16,19	6	8
		Negative	20,21	2	
III.	Empathy	Positive	6,8,10,23,25,26,29,31	8	10
		Negative	13,17	2	
IV.	Handling Relations	Positive	1,2,4,11,14,22,24,27,30	9	9
		Negative	-	-	

Scoring for the Aggression Scale

The Aggression scale consists of 4 factors, Physical Aggression (PA), Verbal Aggression (VA),

Anger (A) and Hostility (H). The total score for Aggression is the sum of the factor scores.

Sr. No.	Dimensions	Items	Serial wise Items No.	Total
I	PA – Physical Aggression	Positive	2,5,8,11,13,22,25,29	9
		Negative	16	
II	VA – Verbal Aggression	Positive	4,6,14,21,27	5
		Negative	-	
III	A – Anger	Positive	1, 12,18, 19,23,28	7
		Negative	9	
IV	H – Hostility	Positive	3,7,10,15,17,20,24,26	8
		Negative	-	

Interpretation: Tally, Compare and Assess with the Means for the standard AQ for High or Average

Buss, A.H. & Perry, M.P. 1992. The Aggression questionnaire. Journal of Psychology and Social Psychology, 63, 452-459

EI questionnaire is to be completed in either “Yes” or “No”.

The Buss & Perry, (1992) Aggression Scale, it's a 5 point scale and with any of the 5 points listed below, one has to indicate how characteristic or uncharacteristic each of the statements is in describing the examinee. One has to place the rating selected next to the item in the box provided.

- I. 1= extremely uncharacteristic of me
- II. 2 = somewhat uncharacteristic of me
- III. 3= neither uncharacteristic nor characteristic of me
- IV. 4= somewhat characteristic of me
- V. 5= extremely characteristic of me

4.1 Results of Descriptive Statics of Study Variables

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statics

Demographic details of the participant					A. Quantitative Interpretation of the EI			
Variable	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	Std. Dev	B.		Emotional Intelligence	Aggression
Male	38	50	-	-	N	Valid	76	76
Female	38	50	-	-		Missing	0	0
Age Group <15 Years	33	43	14	1.1905	Mean		22.86	88.28
Age Group >=15 Years	43	57	15.86	1.1876	Std. Deviation		3.45	15.11
Qualitative Interpretation of the Emotional Intelligence Scores					Variance		11.93	228.443
Range of Scores		Interpretation			Percentiles	25	21	78.5
20 or less		LEI				50	22	88.5
21 to 25		MEI				75	25	99
26 and above		HEI						

*To Note - 50+% of the students fall in the medium level for the variables - Emotional Intelligence Levels and Aggression Levels.

Descriptive Statistics				One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test			
Of the Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	N			Emotional Intelligence	Aggression
Emotional Intelligence	22.86	3.455	76	N		76	76
Aggression	88.28	15.114	76	Normal	Mean	22.86	88.28
Understanding Emotions	2.79	.838	76	Parameters	Std. Deviation	3.455	15.114
Understanding Motivation	5.74	1.320	76	a,b			
Handling Relations	6.87	1.330	76	Most	Absolute	.101	.098
Empathy	7.46	1.483	76	Extreme	Positive	.085	.043
Physical Aggression	27.21	5.947	76	Differences	Negative	-.101	-.098
Verbal Aggression	15.64	3.486	76	Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		.881	.854
Hostility	24.61	5.550	76	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.420	.460
Anger	20.82	5.111	76	a. Test distribution is Normal. b. Calculated from data.			

*One- Sample K-S test was conducted to assess the normality of the data variables.

Distribution of the Levels of the Variables								
Variable Levels	Low		Medium		High		Mean	Std. Dev
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage		
Emotional Intelligence	18	22.22%	41	53.94%	17	20.99%	22.855	.345
Aggression	18	22.22%	43	53.09%	20	24.69%	88.276	15.114

Findings of the Study

Factorial ANOVA – 2 Independent Factors – Gender and EI Levels

The following two-way ANOVA was performed to assess the significant difference in mean Aggression among both genders across all levels of Emotional Intelligence among adolescents in high schools

EI level	(I) Gender	(J) Gender	Mean Difference (I-J)	Sig.	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
LEI	Male	Female	-1.333	.847	8.000	1	8.000	.037	.847
	Female	Male	1.333	.847	15016.905	70	214.527		
MEI	Male	Female	-2.538	.582	65.686	1	65.686	.306	.582
	Female	Male	2.538	.582	15016.905	70	214.527		
HEI	Male	Female	-13.586	.064	760.001	1	760.001	3.543	.064
	Female	Male	13.586	.064	15016.905	70	214.527		

Dependent Variable: Aggression

Each F tests the simple effects of Gender within each level combination of the other effects shown. These tests are based on the linearly independent pairwise comparisons among the estimated marginal means.

Descriptive Statistics				Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Gender		Mean	Std. Deviation	N	Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Male	LEI	93.11	8.448	9	Corrected Model	2116.292 ^a	5	423.258	1.973	.093
	MEI	87.41	15.259	22	Intercept	491149.545	1	491149.545	2289.451	.000
	HEI	73.71	22.801	7	Gender	541.152	1	541.152	2.523	.117
	Total	86.24	16.549	38	Levels	1543.451	2	771.725	3.597	.033
Female	LEI	94.44	9.342	9	Gender *	423.741	2	211.870	.988	.378
	MEI	89.95	13.750	19	Levels					
	HEI	87.30	16.111	10	Total	609379.000	76			
	Total	90.32	13.441	38						
Total	LEI	93.78	8.667	18						
	MEI	88.59	14.455	41						
	HEI	81.71	19.710	17						
	Total	88.28	15.114	76						

a. R Squared = .124 (Adjusted R Squared = .061)
 b. * Test significant at .05 Level
 c. *Aggression is the dependent variable

ANOVA

Figure1 – How Aggression varies with EI Levels

Multiple Comparison – Tukey HSD Test

EI Levels	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Aggression	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
LEI	18	93.78	8.667	Between Groups	1282.606	2	641.303	2.954	0.058
MEI	41	88.59	14.455	Within Groups	15850.59				
HEI	17	81.71	19.71	Total	17133.19				
Total	76	88.28	15.114						

(I) EI Level	(J) EI Level	Mean Difference (I-J)	Sig.
LEI	MEI	5.192	.430
LEI	HEI	12.072*	.047
MEI	LEI	-5.192	.430
MEI	HEI	6.879	.244
HEI	LEI	-12.072*	.047
HEI	MEI	-6.879	.244

1. Dependent Variable: Aggression 2. (*) The mean difference is significant at .05 Level.
3. A Tukey's test was possible as the sample size in both the groups were same.

Figure 2 (below) - The graph above and the table below shows the Tukey simultaneous confidence intervals show that the confidence interval for the difference between the means of LEI and HEI is 5.192 to 12.072. This range does not include zero, which indicates that the difference between these means is significant.

Individual Tests for High School Boys

Multiple Comparison –Tukey's Test

Descriptive Statistics

EI Levels	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
LEI	93.11	8.448	9
MEI	87.41	15.259	22
HEI	73.71	22.801	7
Total	86.24	16.549	38

(I) EI Level	(J) EI Level	Mean Difference (I-J)	Sig. ^a
LEI	MEI	5.70 ^{NS}	.631
	HEI	19.40*	.049
MEI	LEI	-5.70 ^{NS}	.631
	HEI	13.69 ^{NS}	.123
HEI	LEI	-19.40*	.049
	MEI	-13.69 ^{NS}	.123

Note – 1. (*) Mean Difference is significant at .05 Levels 2. Dependent Variable: Aggression

There is a significant difference in the Emotional Intelligence Levels of the adolescent boys in high schools. Considering Aggression as a dependent variable -it indicates that there is a significant difference in Aggression among the boys when their Emotional Intelligence level is lower compared to those boys who showed higher Emotional Intelligence.

Individual Tests for High School Girls

Multiple Comparison –Tukey's Test

Descriptive Statistics

EI Level	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
LEI	94.44	9.342	9
MEI	89.95	13.750	19
HEI	87.30	16.111	10
Total	90.32	13.441	38

(I) EI Level	(J) EI Level	Mean Difference (I-J)	Sig. ^a
LEI	MEI	4.497 ^{NS}	.418
	HEI	7.144 ^{NS}	.259
MEI	LEI	-4.497 ^{NS}	.418
	HEI	2.647 ^{NS}	.620
HEI	LEI	-7.144 ^{NS}	.259
	MEI	-2.647 ^{NS}	.620

1. Dependent Variable: Aggression
2. NS – Mean Difference Not Significant

There is no significant difference in the Emotional Intelligence Levels of the adolescent girls in High Schools, hence no inference on Emotional Intelligence as a contributing factor towards Aggression among girls in high schools.

To substantiate the Post Hoc test – further t tests are conducted later.

Difference between Male and Female high school Students in their Emotional Intelligence

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Emotional Intelligence	Male	38	22.61	3.445	.628 ^{NS}	74	.532
	Female	38	23.11	3.494			

Note – 1. NS – Not Significant 2. **assuming equal Variances

From the above table, it can be inferred that there is no significant difference in the Emotional Intelligence scores of the two groups. This result is not in line with the study conducted by Das P.P., Tripathy S (2015) - on The Role of Emotional Intelligence on Aggression –A comparative study between adolescent boys and girls where the mean difference was significant at .05 level.

Difference between Male and Female high school Students in their Aggression

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Aggression	Male	38	86.24	16.549	1.179 ^{NS}	74	.242
	Female	38	90.32	13.441			

Note – 1. NS – Not Significant 2. **assuming equal Variances

From the above table, the test scores of male and female students indicated their mean differed by 4.08, which highlighted that adolescent girls were more aggressive than boys in these high schools but t test confirmed that the difference is non-significant. This result is not in line with the already existing study conducted by Das P.P., Tripathy S (2015) the Role of Emotional Intelligence on Aggression- a comparison between adolescent boys and girls.

Difference between Male and Female high school Students in their EI Dimensions

EI Dimensions	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Understanding Emotions	Male	38	2.7632	0.7510	0.272 ^{NS}	74	0.786
	Female	38	2.8158	0.9258			
Understanding Motivation	Male	38	5.6316	1.3032	0.693 ^{NS}	74	0.491
	Female	38	5.8421	1.3462			
Empathy	Male	38	7.2632	1.4460	1.163 ^{NS}	74	0.248
	Female	38	7.6579	1.5117			
Handling Relations	Male	38	6.9474	1.3345	0.515 ^{NS}	74	0.608
	Female	38	6.7895	1.3388			

Note – 1. NS – Not Significant **2.** **t value assuming equal Variances

From the above table, it can be inferred that there is no significant difference in the scores of the two groups – male and female on the Emotional Intelligence dimensions.

Difference between Male and Female high school Students in their Aggression Dimensions

Aggression Dimensions	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Physical Aggression	Male	38	27.00	5.457	.307 ^{NS}	74	.760
	Female	38	27.42	6.467			
Verbal Aggression	Male	38	14.97	3.560	1.699 ^{NS}	74	.093
	Female	38	16.32	3.322			
Hostility	Male	38	23.71	6.518	1.415 ^{NS}	74	.161
	Female	38	25.50	4.279			
Anger	Male	38	20.55	5.466	.446 ^{NS}	74	.657
	Female	38	21.08	4.790			

Note – 1. NS – Not Significant **2.** t- value assuming equal Variances

From the above table, it is observed that, the mean scores of the girl students were more than the boys in terms of the Aggression factors, which can be inferred that girls tend to physically harm the other, attack others self-concept and abuse them, a violent tendency to physically assault the target person and getting Angry thereby prepare to attack the opponent were more prominent.

However, a t test confirmed that there is no significant difference in the scores of the two groups – male and female on the Aggression dimensions.

Relationship among the dimensions of Aggression (PA – Physical Aggression, VA- Verbal Aggression, Anger, and Hostility) and Emotional Intelligence (Understanding Emotions, Understanding Motivation, Empathy and Handling Relations) along its variables using Pearson Product Moment Correlation.

Correlation Matrix Emotional Intelligence and Aggression**Correlations using Pearson Product Moment [r]**

N=76	Emotional Intelligence	Aggression	Understanding Emotions	Understanding Motivation	Handling Relations	Empathy	Physical Aggression	Verbal Aggression	Hostility	Anger
1	1	-.203	.528**	.754**	.660**	.768**	-.088	.021	-.328**	-.156
2		1	-.175	.019	-.179	-.231*	.811**	.617**	.780**	.746**
3			1	.299**	.250*	.176	-.133	.088	-.150	-.261*
4				1	.238*	.485**	.078	.185	-.127	-.023
5					1	.288*	-.017	-.171	-.276*	-.092
6						1	-.185	-.012	-.318**	-.114
7							1	.349**	.519**	.433**
8								1	.319**	.389**
9									1	.401**
10										1

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

To examine the relations more closely the Pearson product-moment correlations were examined. A number of significant correlations were observed. Of interest was the significant negative relationship got indicated between Emotional Intelligence and Hostility ($r=-0.328, p<.01$). Hostility also showed a negative correlation with Empathy and Handling Relations respectively ($r= -0.276, p <.01$) and ($r= -0.318, p<.01$). This clearly indicated that Emotional Intelligence or its dimensions increased, the Hostility among students decreased. Empathy and Aggression showed a significant negative relationship ($r=-0.231, p <.05$) indicating if Empathy among students is more, their Aggression level is controlled.

Anger portrayed a negative correlation with Understanding Emotions ($r= -0.261, p <.05$).

To emphasize - Hostility is an overt behaviour to project unfriendliness or opposition to someone’s stimulus, it’s an impulse that drives Aggression towards the other. Whereas, Empathy is an internal ability to sense the other, to feel how they feel. The capacity to place oneself in another's position to understand and share the feelings of another in a given situation. Cognitive empathy is the largely conscious drive to recognize accurately and understand another's emotional state. Sometimes we call this kind of empathy “perspective taking” – which can be developed. Both the variables of Emotional Intelligence and Aggression are dimensionally opposite variables which controls one another.

Multiple Regression Table of Factors in Emotional Intelligence and Aggression amongst adolescent students in high schools to establish the significance

Figure 3a.

Figure 3b.

Figure 3c.

The above Figures conclude - A Reasonably good fit after outlier analysis of Figure (3c) did consider the single point outside the range with Mahalanobis distance validation.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error				Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance	VIF
Empathy	-2.351	1.15	-.231	2.039	.045	-4.649	-.054	1.000	1.000

Tolerance Less than .10 indicates no multicollinearity

b) VIF Less than 10 indicates no multicollinearity

Model	Variables Entered	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	Empathy	.231 ^a	.053	.040	14.806	2.201

a. Predictors: (Constant), Empathy

b. Dependent Variable: Aggression

c. A smaller sample size have led to higher Error of Estimation

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	911.496	1	911.496	4.158	.045 ^b
	Residual	16221.702	74	219.212		
	Total	17133.197	75			

a. Dependent Variable: Aggression

b. Predictors: (Constant), Empathy

c. Statistically significant hence it does a good job to predict the true state of the population outcome better than just a chance model.

d. Empathy is the independent variable that contributed the most to the outcome model – significant and unique contribution to the prediction of the outcome.

The above model clearly shows that Empathy significantly affects the Aggression (at .05 level) with Beta Value - .231

Summary

Major responsibility to handle the most sensitive phase of adolescence - lies in the hands of his family. Well behaved children grow up well nurtured not just because of a balanced upbringing but also observing well behaved parents. Thus parenting gets tougher!

Every parent has to teach their child if one lesson to be emotionally erudite. That is the skill the child will need in order to overcome stress, anxiety, frustration, disappointment, anger, hurt and despair thereafter in life. They would need to appraise their child that difficult situations in life help to improve our self-esteem, courage, and self-reliance, which in turn enable us to handle life on our own terms.

Aggression is a by-product of the Emotional dilemma of a growing child which takes various shapes in adolescence. This study intends to assess the relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Aggression level of high school students from various perspective.

Study was conducted on 76 samples consisting of equal number of boys and girls in their adolescent phase as students from various high schools. Under this broad survey method, the questionnaire of data collection is utilized in the study. Data was collected using Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire by Dr Arun Singh and Dr Shruti Narayan, 2014. The Buss-Perry Aggression Questionnaire (Buss & Perry, 1992) is used to measure Aggression and its dimensions.

Major Findings from this Study

The following inferences were made after the evaluation and analysis of the data.

- There is no significant difference between Emotional Intelligence scores of the male and the female high schools students.
- There is no significant difference between the Aggression Scores of the male and high school students.
- Significant negative relationship got indicated between Emotional Intelligence and Hostility ($r = -0.328$, $p < .01$). Hostility also showed a negative correlation with Empathy and Handling Relations respectively ($r = -0.276$, $p < .01$) and ($r = -0.318$, $p < .01$). This clearly indicated that Emotional Intelligence or its dimensions increased, the Hostility among students decreased. Empathy and Aggression showed a significant negative relationship ($r = -0.231$, $p < .05$) indicating if Empathy among students is more, their Aggression level is controlled. Anger portrayed a negative correlation with Understanding Emotions ($r = -0.261$, $p < .05$). The regression model emphasised the significant contribution of Empathy towards reducing Aggression amongst adolescents.
- Tukey simultaneous confidence intervals showed significant difference in the confidence interval for the difference between the mean range of LEI and HEI as 5.192 to 12.072. There exists a significant difference in-between group levels of emotional intelligence (HEI, MEI & LEI) on aggression of adolescent male students but not female students. Tukey simultaneous difference between the group on aggression across the various Emotional levels of the male and female students indicated significant difference in LEI and HEI at .05 level. This indicates that higher levels of Emotional Intelligence among adolescents can show reduced Aggression tendencies.

Limitations of the Study

- Sampling Technique - The sample of the present study was drawn from very few matriculation and higher secondary schools and may have a geographical limitations based on the schools participating in the survey.
- The study is restricted to a convenient technique with 76 adolescent students of the high schools (38 boys and 38 girls only).
- Behavioural differences - Adolescents may have a desire to “fake good” or an attempt to give results that will please others, hence responses may not be full proof.
- Additional extraneous variables may account for some of the correlations demonstrated in the study. (For example, it is possible that characteristics such as general intelligence might affect both the adolescent aggression and Emotional Intelligence.)

- Testing bias is a possible limitation of the study. Both questionnaires were administered at the same time and in the same location. This creates a possibility that one questionnaire may have affected the answers given of the other questionnaire.

Implications of the Study

The study gave us an insight into the investigation about what Emotional Intelligence variables contribute to Aggression causing variables positively or negatively.

Recommendations for Further Research

Emotional Intelligence is a fairly newer concept in the emerging field of psychology. Currently there are measurement and definitional issues surrounding the concept of Emotional Intelligence. The depth and width of the concept is yet to be standardized as a psychological term. The literature continues to struggle with a working model. Further research is needed to investigate the psychometric status of Emotional Intelligence and to determine whether it serves as a unique human ability. Balancing or Improving ID (Rationale) in the personality as per Psychoanalytic theory serves to control many of the struggles within the human mind.

Many other research idea generated by this study. Further work on stress management and stress management programs is justified. Programs which develop stress management techniques and studies which examine their utility would be beneficial.

A further examination of gender differences, aggression and emotional intelligence is warranted. Do the gender differences in Emotional Intelligence increase with varying Age? Do post adolescents and aged people demonstrate the same differences in Emotional Intelligence as adolescents? Further research regarding these variables and possible positive and negative correlation needs to be studied.

Although there is no significant relationship between the overall Emotional Intelligence and Aggression scores among male and female students, a study is possible to understand if high grades or performance in school is a contributing factor to the Emotional Intelligence scores. Emotional Intelligence scores and other standardized test may stand to reason that an adolescent in control of his or her emotions may outperform a peer in many areas if the peer did not have the same emotional control.

An examination of the psychometric properties of the Aggression questionnaire when dealing with adolescent is warranted. Can the four model of the questionnaire be replicated when dealing with the adolescents?

There continues to be many under substantiated claims regarding the importance of Emotional Intelligence (Goleman 1995). It is important to examine the role emotional intelligence might play in various different aspects of human functioning. Some examples might include Career Success, Annual Income, Job Satisfaction, and Family Life Balance, University or College Undergraduate success.

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